

Application of Probabilistic Safety Analysis to the Emergency Scenarios Assessment of a Loss of Coolant Accidents in the VVER-Reactor Plant

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Probabilistic safety analysis of loss of coolant accidents (LOCA) in the VVER-reactor plant has been performed, taking into account the internal initiating events of the reactor primary circuit middle leakages. Logical probabilistic models of the accident scenarios of the middle primary circuit leakages were developed taking into account different operation modes of reactor plant. Critical paths and probabilities of the accident scenarios were identified. Program code RiskSpectrum PSA was used for probabilistic safety analysis. Recommendations for increase of reliability of systems safety functions during the middle leakages accidents were given.

PACS numbers: 87.53.Bn,88.05.Lg

Keywords: probabilistic safety assessment, safety of nuclear power plant, accident scenarios

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10889768>

1. Introduction

The development of the nuclear power engineering makes the increased requirements on ensuring safety principles in the power industry and conducting qualitative and quantitative analysis of accidents scenarios with an assessment of the safety level of nuclear power plants (NPP).

The probabilistic safety analysis (PSA) of nuclear power plants is one of the main tools (along with deterministic analysis) for assessing the safety of nuclear power plants. Using the accumulated statistical data on equipment defects and NPP malfunctions, the PSA makes it possible, based on probabilistic calculations, to assess the safety level of operating nuclear power plants [1].

PSA makes it possible to create a consistent integral model of the plant's behavior from a safety point of view, and accordingly, it allows for a reliable basis for making decisions in the field of safety.

The objects of the PSA study are sources of radioactivity at the reactor core and spent nuclear fuel pool. A full-scale PSA must be performed for all three levels, including the determination of the probability of the reactor core damage (CDP) or reactor core damage frequency (CDF), that's the task of PSA level 1; the probability of an accidental release (PSA level 2) and the consequences of releases (assessment of the risk of death and possible damage, PSA level 3) [2].

In accordance with the structure of the PSA, the risk from the operation of a power unit can be described as [3]:

$$R_c = \sum_i \sum_j \sum_k [F_i \cdot P_{(i/j)}] \cdot P_{(j/k)} \cdot C_{(k/c)}, \quad (1)$$

where R_c is the risk of consequences c (number of deaths/year); F_i is the frequency of the initiating event (1/year); $P_{i/j}$ is the conditional probability that initiating event will lead to the damage to the radioactivity source (CDRS) j ; $P_{j/k}$ is the conditional probability that CDRS j will lead to releases of radioactive substances k ; $C_{k/c}$ is the number of deaths caused by emissions of radioactive substances k .

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Determining all the factors on the right side of equation (1) is a PSA level 3 task. Determining the third factor on the right side of the equation is a PSA level 2 task. Determining the first two factors in (1) is a PSA level 1 task.

The numerical indicator of NPP safety within the framework of PSA level 1 is the total frequency of severe accidents associated with reactor core damage (CDF). The target value of CDF is $1E-5$ for one nuclear power plant unit over interval of one year [2].

To determine CDF, it is necessary to consider the entire spectrum of possible accidents with unsuccessful end states. It should be noted that even low probability (frequency) of unsuccessful end states of the accidents cannot be excluded from the analysis results, since this quantity contributes to the total value of CDF. Excluding accidents with low probability may distort the total value of CDF and will not allow reliably access the safety of NPP unit.

Risk is understood as the product of the probability of undesirable event and the of damage from it [3]. Sometimes an event has a low probability, but the possible damage is so great that risk from the event cannot be neglected.

If the assessment of CDF does not confirm the fulfillment of targets, then the NPP design must provide the additional technical solutions (including special technical means for beyond design accident management) in order to reduce the probability of accidents and mitigate their consequences.

The main task of accident assessment is the development of probabilistic safety models, which are used as event trees and fault trees. The event tree is a logical diagram that determines the set of possible end states (ES) of the NPP, each of which is the implementation of certain combination sets of intermediate events for a given initiating event (IE). The development of accident sequences (event trees) is considered for initiating event depending on the plant operation state of the power unit before the IE, the characteristics of the IE, configuration of the systems necessary to perform the safety functions, performance/failure

of the safety functions [2].

Middle leaks of the reactor primary circuit are the serious accidents leading to loss of reactor core cooling that can lead to a severe accident with fuel damage and radioactive releases beyond the reactor containment. The main aspect of accident analysis is to determine the critical paths of accident sequences and develop recommendations to reduce the probability of severe accident.

The purpose of the work is to develop the logical probabilistic models of the reactor primary circuit middle leakages accidents for nuclear power plants with WWER reactors and assess the critical paths and probabilities of the accident consequences taking into account the parameters of the leaks, plant operation states, configuration of the safety systems and other parameters.

2. Probabilistic accident sequence analysis for primary circuit middle leakages in the VVER-reactor plant

Probabilistic accident sequence analysis for primary circuit middle leakages in the VVER-reactor plant has been performed using the development of the logical probabilistic models of the NPP unit. Calculations of results were performed using the program code RiskSpectrum PSA [4].

To carry out the probabilistic calculations, it was necessary to determine the set of successful (OK) and unsuccessful (CD) end states of the accident scenarios. The characteristics of end states use the values of the probabilities of their implementation and functional minimal cut sets. The minimal cut sets is understood as the minimal combination of basic events (including failures of system elements, human errors), as a result of which a negative consequence is realized.

The criterion for unsuccessful accident end states is the excess of at least one maximum design limit, characterizing nuclear fuel damage [5]:

- the maximum temperature of the fuel cladding during the entire period of the accident scenarios does not exceed 1200°C;
- the depth of local oxidation of the fuel shell is not more than 18 % of the initial thickness of the shell;
- radially averaged fuel enthalpy does not exceed 963 J/g UO₂ along the axis of any fuel element.

A successful end state (safe state) is understood as a stable state of a reactor facility with a sub-critical state of nuclear fuel and not exceeding of the above criteria during the accident. Analysis of the list of dominant minimal cut set allows to identify elements (combinations of elements) of systems and human errors that make the greatest contribution to reducing the safety of a power unit, as well as develop recommendations for improving safety.

In the process of probabilistic assessment of the initiating events of accidents or safety systems of nuclear power plants, the significance of the basic events (failures) is analyzed using the Fussel-Vessely (*FV*) and Birnbaum (*FB*) values, and also the risk change coefficients are determined: Risk Decrease Factor (*RDF*) and Risk Increase Factor (*RIF*) [1, 3]. The Fussel-Vessely (*FV*) value of event *X* is defined as the relative contribution of the event to the probability of a severe accident. The Fussel-Vessely significance can be expressed as the sum of the contributions of the minimal cut sets containing the *X* event:

$$FV = \frac{F(X) - F(0)}{F(X)}, \quad (2)$$

where $F(X)$ is the probability of a severe accident or the probability of system failure at the nominal probability of the basic event, and $F(0)$ is the assumption that the event did not occur.

The Birnbaum significance indicator of event *X* is defined as the ratio of the change in the probability of severe accident to the change in

the probability of the occurrence of event *X* (derivative):

$$B(x) = \frac{d}{dx} P(x) \quad (3)$$

or

$$B(x) = F(1) - F(0), \quad (4)$$

where $F(1)$ is the probability of severe accident under the assumption that the event occurred, and $F(0)$ is under the assumption that the event did not occur. Thus Birnbaum's Fussel-Vessely measure of significance is the difference between the probability of severe accident calculated under the assumption that event *X* occurred and the probability of severe accident calculated under the assumption that event *X* did not occur.

The risk reduction coefficient (*RDF*) shows a decrease in probability of severe accident with absolute reliability of the element (probability of failure is 0). Thereby, *RDF* defines a set of system elements, the increase in reliability of which allows increase the reliability of the power unit at the lowest cost:

$$RDF = \frac{F(x)}{F(0)}. \quad (5)$$

The risk increase coefficient shows an increase in severe accident probability with absolute unreliability of the element (probability of failure is 1), making it possible to identify system elements that significantly affect the decrease in the reliability of the power unit:

$$RIF = \frac{F(1)}{F(X)}. \quad (6)$$

Middle leakage accidents of nuclear power plant (NPP) unit occur as a result of breaks in the "cold" or "hot" loops of the reactor primary circuit or pipelines of systems associated with that. Graphical representation of the primary circuit of a VVER-reactor plant is presented in Figure 1 [6].

The following processes occur during the middle leak accidents. The middle leakages of

FIG. 1: (Color online) Graphical representation of the primary circuit of VVER-type reactor plant.

the primary circuit in a power unit with a VVER type reactor causes a sharp decrease in the circuit pressure, the coolant level in the reactor pressurizer vessel (RPV), and the loss of the first circuit coolant with a potential risk of exposure and damage of the reactor core [5, 6]. After emptying the reactor pressurizer vessel and exposing the "hot" nozzles of the reactor, the circulation of the primary circuit coolant is disrupted and the heat removal from the core through the steam generators is terminated. The process leads to core exposure followed by its coolant flooding from the hydraulic accumulator tanks and emergency high and low pressure injection system pumps. The end state of plant unit is cold shutdown, which is required for any primary circuit leakage.

Analysis of the list of dominant minimal cut sets allows to identify elements (combinations of elements) of systems and operator errors

that make the greatest contribution to reducing the safety of a power unit, as well as develop recommendations for improving safety. Depending on the development of the accident, the configuration of the safety systems required to perform safety functions (feed-up systems of the first circuit, heat removal systems through the primary and second circuits), middle leaks of the primary circuit are divided into several ranges with an equivalent diameter of 80-140 mm.

The range of middle leaks in the reactor first circuit, initiating events LM1, LM2, includes leaks in the circulation loops of the first circuit, connection lines of hydraulic accumulation tanks and active part of emergency core coolant system, leaks in the pipeline to the reactor pressurizer vessel. Depending on the place of the leak, some trains of the low pressure emergency core coolant system (LP ECCS) and high pressure emergency core coolant system (HP ECCS), as

well as hydraulic accumulation tanks, may not be available [7].

Middle leaks of the primary circuit have a low frequency of occurrence, for example, for the reactor plant with VVER-1200, the frequency of leakage of the first circuit LM1 is $5.33\text{E-}07$, LM2 - $3.78\text{E-}07$, however, the development such an accident process can cause a severe accident with damage of the nuclear fuel in the reactor, releases of radioactive substances into environment. So middle leaks accidents require careful study to determine the critical paths and the main contributors to the probability of this accident.

Logical probabilistic models of the accident scenarios of the middle primary circuit leakages in the VVER-type reactor were developed for assessment of the probability of this accident. For different plant operation states (POS) of NPP unit several separate event trees are developed using the POS functional event. Accident sequences for LM1 middle leak during power unit operation is presented in Figure 2.

Accident sequences for IE LM1 during shutdown unit operation is presented in Figure 3.

The result of the analysis of the accepted sequences and performed calculations of lists of minimum cut sets were obtained (see Figure 4).

The probability of occurrence of middle leak LM1 is rather small and amounts to $5.33\text{E-}07$, the reliability of safety functions is also quite high, as a result of that the probability of accident sequences with unsuccessful end states (CD) during unit power operation mode ranges from $4.71\text{E-}10$ up to $4.25\text{E-}14$. The article provides probability values with three significant figures due to the structure of the results presentation in the program code RiskSpectrum.

The critical path for the development of middle leak accident LM1 is the sequence with a leak in the pipeline to the reactor pressurizer vessel. For the power operating mode that probability is $4.71\text{E-}10$, for shutdown modes the probability of such end state is $6.06\text{E-}12$.

The uncertainty analysis for the accident

sequence was performed. The boundaries of the 90 % confidence interval were obtained (during unit power operating): the lower limit (5 %) is $8.70\text{E-}11$, median (50%) is $4.27\text{E-}10$, upper limit (95 %) is $1.04\text{E-}9$. When the unit is operating in shutdown modes, the limits of the 90-percent confidence interval are: the lower limit (5 %) is $1.39\text{E-}12$, the median (50 %) is $3.51\text{E-}11$, the upper limit (95 %) is $2.81\text{E-}10$.

The greatest contribution to the failure of safety functions during the initiating event LM1 is made by the minimum cut sets with failures due to common causes of the supporting systems (ventilation systems, the cooling circuit of the critical consumers (KAA), refrigeration equipment). Operation of these systems during shutdown mode becomes significant, since it is necessary to carry out a long-term removal of residual heat from the reactor core using equipment of these systems. Figure 5 shows the diagram of the contributions of the dominant minimal cut sets for LM1 during power operation of NPP unit.

Analysis of the middle leak LM2 shows that the probability of the end states with damage of nuclear fuel is $5.89\text{E-}9$ under power operating mode, and while shutdown operating modes the total probability is $5.43\text{E-}11$. The critical path for the development of an accident with a middle leak LM2 is an accident sequence with the leak in the pipeline to the reactor pressurizer vessel in all operating modes.

For the reliable performance of safety functions by systems in the middle leak accident LM1 and LM2 during all operation states, it is necessary to ensure not only the reliable operation of the main equipment of the safety systems, but also to increase the reliability of supporting systems, including by changing the maintenance procedures and equipment performance checks.

Analysis of the RDF factor of the primary circuit middle leak LM1 shows that the most significant are the elements of the supporting systems, such as the refrigeration re-circulation system (KLG) and the cooling circuit of the critical consumers (KAA), since their effective

FIG. 2: Accident sequences for LM1 middle leak during power unit operation.

FIG. 3: Accident sequences for LM1 middle leak during shutdown unit operation.

operation affects the performance of system security functions. Increasing the reliability of the operation of these supporting systems will significantly and the most effectively improve the

reliability of the residual heat removal safety functions in the reactor.

The critical path for the development of accidents with the middle leaks LM1 and LM2 is

Top Event frequency F = 4.360E-10

No	Probability	%	Event 1	Event 2	Event 3	Event 4
1	1.29E-10	29.61	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AA60YVCO-ALL	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
2	5.85E-11	13.42	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AA60YVCO-3AA	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
3	3.38E-11	07.75	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AA60ZVCO-ALL	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
4	2.70E-11	06.20	IE-LM1	KLZGZ1AN001FAS-ALL	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
5	2.04E-11	04.69	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AA60ZVCO-3AA	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
6	1.81E-11	04.15	IE-LM1	KLZGZ1AN001FAS-3AA	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
7	1.70E-11	03.91	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AP001PMS-ALL	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
8	1.25E-11	02.87	IE-LM1	CLZ53U4.ZZJPF-ALL	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
9	1.09E-11	02.50	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AP001PMS-3AA	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
10	1.01E-11	02.32	IE-LM1	KLZGZ1AN001FAR-ALL	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
11	6.57E-12	01.51	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AP001PMR-3AA	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
12	6.55E-12	01.50	IE-LM1	CLRXYYSU23.1CSF-AL	_POS14(LM)	
13	6.55E-12	01.50	IE-LM1	CLRXYYSU14.2CSF-AL	_POS14(LM)	
14	6.55E-12	01.50	IE-LM1	CLRXYYSU23.2CSF-AL	_POS14(LM)	
15	6.55E-12	01.50	IE-LM1	CLRXYYSU14.1CSF-AL	_POS14(LM)	
16	6.20E-12	01.42	IE-LM1	CLZ53U4.ZZJPF-3AB	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
17	5.69E-12	01.31	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AP001PMR-ALL	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
18	5.03E-12	01.15	IE-LM1	KLZGZ1AN001FAR-3AA	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
19	2.84E-12	00.65	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AA601VCO-ALL	_DP_LM1	_POS14(LM)
20	2.10E-12	00.48	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AA60YVCO-ALL	_DL4_LM1	_POS14(LM)
21	2.10E-12	00.48	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AA60YVCO-ALL	_DL3_LM1	_POS14(LM)
22	2.10E-12	00.48	IE-LM1	JNDZ0AA60YVCO-ALL	_DL2_LM1	_POS14(LM)

FIG. 4: (Color online) Results of minimal cut set analysis for middle leaks during power unit operation.

an accident sequence with the leaks in the pipeline to the reactor pressurizer vessel in all operating modes.

The greatest contribution to the failure of safety functions during the initiating events LM1 and LM2 is made by the minimum cut sets with failures due to common causes of the main equipment of the safety systems (pumps, control valves) and some elements of supporting systems.

Analysis of cut set list did not reveal any significant human errors. That means that power unit is significantly protected from the influence of erroneous human actions during management of the middle leaks accidents.

The constant efforts of developers to improve the reliability of structure and components of the reactor safety systems significantly reduce the risk of their failures. In this regard, the dominant minimal cut sets, that make the greatest contribution to the failure of safety functions

include common cause failures (failures of identical elements performing identical functions due to similar reasons). These minimal cut sets are highlighted in purple in Fig. 2. The principal of redundancy of systems and elements does not allow us to exclude common cause failures. An effective solution in this case is the principle of diversification: the use of different device design, different device drivers (for example, electric or diesel drivers for pumps), different equipment manufactures, etc. in addition. The solution of the problem can be to change the procedure of repair and maintenance of redundant system elements in order to eliminate latent equipment failures in standby modes.

FIG. 5. Diagram of the contributions of the dominant minimal cut sets for LM1 leak during power operation of NPP unit.

3. Conclusion

The probabilistic safety analysis of the reactor primary circuit middle leakages was performed. The following tasks were solved:

- development of the probabilistic logical models of the middle leakages accident scenarios for the primary circuit of the VVER-type reactor plant;
- identifying the critical paths and probability of accident sequences;
- identifying the most significant contributors to reducing the safety of the reactor plant;
- performing an uncertainty analysis of the results;
- developing the recommendations for improving reliability and safety of the operation of the NPP union with a WWER-type reactor.

The results of the work make it possible to develop recommendations for improving reliability and safety of the operation of the NPP union with a WWER-type reactor.

For the reliable performance of safety functions by systems during the middle leak accidents under all operation states, it is necessary to pay attention to the problem of common cause faults of the main equipment of the safety systems, and also to increase the reliability of supporting systems by changing the maintenance procedures and equipment performance checks.

The results of the work and recommendations can be used when developing

technical decisions to reduce the probability of middle leaks accidents and the risk of severe accidents with radioactive releases.

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